

Lithium Aluminium Hydride Reduction of Nitrosteroids

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The reaction of 3 β -acetoxy-6-nitro-7 α -bromocholest-5-ene (1) with lithium aluminium hydride gave 6-nitrocholest-3,5-diene (2), 3 β -acetoxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one oxime (3), 3 β hydroxy-6 β -nitrocholest-4-ene (4), 3 β -hydroxy-6 β -nitro-7 α -bromocholest-4-ene (5), 3 β -hydroxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (6) and 3 β -hydroxy-6-amincholest-5-ene (7). Under similar reaction conditions, 3 β -chloro-6-nitro-7 α -bromocholest-5-ene (8) afforded 3 β -chloro-5 α -cholestan-6-one oxime (9) and 3 β -chloro-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (10). The structures of these compounds were established on the basis of their spectral data and comparison with authentic samples wherever available.

REDUCTION of nitroolefins by a variety of procedures are described in literature¹⁻⁵. The present was undertaken in order to extend the scope of reaction with lithium aluminium hydride and to check the products distribution when the bromine atom is present at position C-7 of nitroolefins. Treatment of 3 β -acetoxy-6-nitro-7 α -bromocholest-5-ene (1) in dry ether with lithium aluminium hydride afforded compounds 2-7. Under similar reaction conditions, 3 β -chloro-6-nitro-7 α -bromocholest-5-ene (8) gave compounds 9-10. The structures of the compounds were established on the basis of spectral and chemical evidences.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were determined on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer, and nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian A60 instrument with tetramethyl silane as the internal standard. Tlc plates were prepared from silica gel G and sprayed with 20% aqueous perchloric acid. Light petroleum refers to a fraction of b.p. 60-80°. Anhydrous sodium sulphate was used as drying agent.

Reaction of 1 with lithium aluminium hydride: 3 β -Acetoxy-6-nitro-7 α -bromocholest-5-ene (1; 3.0 g)¹⁰ dissolved in dry ether was added to lithium aluminium hydride complex (3.0 g lithium aluminium hydride dissolved in 100 ml dry ether) dropwise at room temperature. The reaction mixture was stirred for 30 h, then ethyl acetate and HCl (50%; 50 ml) were added to it and the solution was filtered. The filtrate was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of the solvents gave an oily residue (3.20 g), which was chromatographed over silica gel (60 g). Elution with light petroleum gave 2^o which was recrystallised from methanol (200 mg), m.p. and m.m.p. 72° (Found: C, 78.40; H, 10.39; N, 3.35. C₂₇H₄₅NO₂ calcd. for: C, 78.45; H, 10.41; N, 3.38%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 680 (C=C-C=C-NO₂), 1 630 (C=C), 1 508 and 1 360 cm⁻¹ (C-NO₂); δ 6.5 (d, *J* 10 Hz, C4-H), 6.0 (m, C3-H), 1.05, 0.90, 0.82 and 0.76 (for 5-methyl protons). Elution with light petroleum ether (5:1) afforded 3^o, which was recrystallised from methanol (500 mg), m.p. and m.m.p. 200° (Found: C, 75.80; H, 9.98; N, 3.04. C₂₇H₄₅NO₂ calcd. for: C, 75.81; H 10.02; N 3.05%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 450-3 154 (=NOH), 1 735 (CH₃COO), 1 680 (C=N), 1 240 and 1 040 cm⁻¹ (C-O); δ 5.2 (m, *W*_{1/2} 16 Hz, C3- α -H), 3.48 (d, C7-H₂), 8.7 (br, OH, exchangeable with deuterium), 2.0 (s, CH₃COO), 1.2, 0.86, 0.80 and 0.65 (other methyl protons). Further elution with light petroleum ether (3:1) yielded 4^o which was recrystallised from petroleum ether (400 mg), m.p. and m.m.p. 154° (Found: C, 75.98; H, 10.30; N, 3.28. C₂₇H₄₅NO₂ calcd. for: C, 75.11; H, 10.35; N, 3.23%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 420 (OH), 1 620 (C=C), 1 535, 1 350 and 1 370 cm⁻¹ (conjugated NO₂); δ 5.85 (brs, C4-vinyl H), 4.62 (dd, *J*_{ae} 4, *J*_{ee} 2 Hz, C6- α H), 4.12 (m, *W*_{1/2} 18 Hz, C3- α -H), 1.2, 0.93, 0.83 and 0.73 (remaining methyl protons). Elution with light petroleum ether (2:1), gave 5 as an oil (300 mg) which failed to crystallise and gave positive Beilstein test for halogen (Found: C, 63.53; H, 8.64; N, 2.76. C₂₇H₄₄NO₂Br calcd. for: C, 63.52; H, 8.62; N, 2.74%; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 420 (OH), 1 630 (C=C), 1 535, 1 345 and 1 375

(-NO₂) and 765 cm⁻¹ (CBr); δ 5.84 (brs, C4-vinyl H), 5.16 (brs, C7-β-H, pseudoequatorial), 4.61 (brm, C6-α-H), 3.9 (br, W_{1/2} 20 Hz, C3-α-H), 1.0, 0.93, 0.84 and 0.67 (other methyl protons). Further elution with light petroleum ether (1 : 1) afforded 6^o which was recrystallised from methanol (200 mg), m.p. and m.m.p. 129° (Found : C, 75.20; H, 10.47; N, 3.35. C₂₇H₄₅NO₂ calcd. for : C, 75.17; H, 10.44; N, 3.24%); ν_{max} 3 400 (OH), 1 620 (C=C), 1 540 and 1 390 cm⁻¹ (C-NO₂); δ 4.25 (br, W_{1/2} 18 Hz, C3-α-H), 2.1 (br, C4, C7-allylic protons), 1.0, 0.9, 0.8 and 0.7 (5-methyl protons). Finally, elution with ether yielded 7 which was recrystallised from methanol (800 mg) m.p. 148° (Found : C, 80.81; H, 11.71; N, 3.50. C₂₇H₄₇NO calcd. for : C, 80.79; H, 11.72; N, 3.49%); ν_{max} 3 340 (OH), 3 260 (NH) and 1 630 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ 3.8 (brs, NH₂, exchangeable with deuterium), 3.45 (br, W_{1/2} 18 Hz, C3-α-H), 1.0, 0.9, 0.8 and 0.6 (other methyl protons).

Reaction of 8 with lithium aluminium hydride : Under similar reaction conditions-3β-chloro-6-nitro-7α-bromocholest-5-ene (8)¹⁰ provided 9 and 10. The same amounts of reactants were used and the resulting oily residue was chromatographed. Elution with light petroleum ether-ether (10 : 1) gave 9¹¹ which was crystallised from methanol, (1.0 g), m.p. and m.m.p. 174° (Found : C, 74.40; H, 10.6; N, 3.23. C₂₇H₄₆NOCl calcd. for : C, 74.39; H, 10.59; N, 3.21%); ν_{max} 3 440-3 200 (=NOH), 1 680 (C=N) and 740 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); δ 3.48 (d, C7-H₂), 8.5(1H, br, OH, exchangeable with deuterium), 3.6(1H, brs, W_{1/2} 16 Hz, C3-α-H), methyl signals

were present at 1.17, 1.2, 0.9 and 0.7. Elution with light petroleum ether-ether (5 : 1) afforded 10¹² which was recrystallised from acetone (750 mg), m.p. and m.m.p. 152° (Found : C, 72.20; H, 9.81; N, 3.80. C₂₇H₄₄NO₂Cl calcd. for : C, 72.16; H, 9.79; N, 3.11%); ν_{max} 1 620 (C=C), 1 545 and 1 375 (NO₂) and 740 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); δ 4.15 (br, W_{1/2} 18 Hz, C3-α-H), 1.0, 0.92, 0.82 and 0.7 (5-methyl protons).

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